

HarSval

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"Project: HarSval Bilateral initiative aiming at Harmonisation of the Svalbard cooperation."

Joint pilot studies concerning impact of Arctic climate change on marine and coastal environment in the northern and eastern Svalbard key areas and paleogeographical and thermal evolution of Svalbard

REPORT FROM TASK 1.2.1 COASTAL ZONE CHANGES AND GEOHAZARDS

Background

The present state of research into coastal change in Svalbard reflects a growing recognition of the complex interactions between climate change, glacial dynamics and coastal ecosystems. Recent studies have highlighted significant transformations in the coastal landscape, driven primarily by accelerated glacier retreat and the resulting geomorphological changes. For instance, Kavan & Strzelecki (2023) have documented a shift from marine-terminating glaciers to land-based glaciers, resulting in the formation of approximately 922.9 km of new coastline since the 1930s. This indicates a substantial alteration in coastal dynamics due to climate-induced glacier decay. Research has also emphasised the role of coastal erosion and sediment dynamics in shaping Svalbard's coastlines. Węślawski & Urbański (2024) emphasise that soft sediment shores, characterised by sandy and gravel beaches, are dynamic habitats that support limited species diversity, primarily interstitial meiofauna. This highlights the ecological implications of coastal changes, as shifts in sediment supply and erosion rates can significantly impact local biodiversity. Furthermore, studies by Aga et al. (2024) reveal that coastal retreat rates for high-Arctic rock cliffs have accelerated over the past decade, suggesting that even previously stable coastal features are now vulnerable to climate change. The influence of changing hydrographic conditions on coastal ecosystems is another critical area of research. For instance, the influx of warmer Atlantic waters into Svalbard's fjords has been linked to reduced ice formation and altered marine habitats, which may facilitate the introduction of more temperate species (Vacquie-Garcia et al., 2018). This shift in marine biodiversity is indicative of broader ecological changes occurring in response to climate warming. Moreover, the research conducted by Nicu et al. (2020) underscores the dual pressures exerted by both natural and anthropogenic factors on coastal regions, particularly with regard to cultural heritage sites that are progressively vulnerable to the threat of coastal erosion.

Moreover, the socio-economic ramifications of these environmental changes are becoming increasingly evident. Jaskólski et al. (2018) observe that Svalbard functions as a barometer for environmental and economic change, with coastal zones proving particularly sensitive to climate shifts and human impacts. The challenges posed by coastal hazards, such as erosion and infrastructure stability, are critical for communities like Longyearbyen, where adaptation strategies are necessary to address the impacts of climate change and increasing tourism (Tanguy et al., 2024; Hovelsrud et al., 2020). Importantly, most of the coastal research to date has been carried out along the west coast of Svalbard, so in the HarSval project we decided to carry out preliminary research along the coasts of the eastern regions.

In summary, the current state of Svalbard coastal change research is characterised by a multidisciplinary approach that integrates glaciology, ecology, and socio-economic factors. The findings indicate that Svalbard's coastal environments are undergoing rapid transformations due to climate change, with significant implications for both natural ecosystems and human activities.

Goal: The overarching aim of the component aimed to investigate the impact of coastal hazards on the stability of coastal systems as well as coastal pollution along new coastal zones emerging from melting ice along the eastern coast of Svalbard (incl. eastern Spitsbergen, Barentsøya and Edgeøya). To do so scientific team from the University of Wrocław, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Institute of Geophysics PAS, Institute of Oceanology PAS, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, University of Bergen, University Centre in Svalbard, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research NIKU targeted study sites that were never subject to joint Polish-Norwegian cooperation (Figure 1) and are largely unexplored. During the scientific cruise (Figure 3) organized in August 2024 particular focus was paid on cultural heritage sites threatened by the coastal erosion (especially cultural heritage sites that are included in the "Catalogue of cultural heritage sites with high priority in Svalbard"), and coastal archives (lakes, lagoon, beach ridge plains) that may contain important palaeogeographical information on analogous past climate changes and extreme events, but are also prone to degradation.

Figure 1. Scientific cruise participants: University of Wroclaw (Matt Strzelecki, Iwo Wieczorek), University of Bergen (Willem van der Bilt + guest research Wim Hoek), UiT The Arctic University of Norway (Anders Schomaker), Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Sciences (Zuza Świrad), Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research NIKU (Cris Nicu), Institute of Oceanology PAS (Agnieszka Kalinowska).

Figure 2. SY Ocean B crew Captain: Andrzej Górajek (right), and crew member Wojciech Pasieczny (left). Third member of the crew Halina Górajek

Figure 3. Route of HarSval scientific cruise along the eastern coast of Svalbard - August 2025. 1 – Aghardbukta, 2 – Heleysundet, 3 – Svenskøya, 4 – Sundeneset (Barentsøya), 5- Russebukta, 6 – Calypsostranda – revisit of CRIOS project monitoring site.

Figure 4. Example of cultural heritage - small cabin in Agardhbukta

Figure 5. Ruins of former trappers cabin in Bucholzbukta.

Figure 6. One of the last remaining cabins on Svenskoya threatened by accelerated coastal erosion.

Figure 7. Wurzbürgerhytta situated on a stable rocky coast of Freemansundet.

Figure 8. Remnants of Pomor's village in Russebukta, Edgoya.

Figure 9. Revisit of permafrost monitoring site in Calypsostranda installed during the previous Polish-Norwegian project CRIOS.

Preliminary results:

Plastic pollution and water chemistry of coastal ponds along shores of Eastern Svalbard

As part of the HarSval project, tasks related to the Land Promontories Project (RIS 12284) were carried out. The objective was to verify the correlation between the presence of driftwood on the shores of Svalbard and the deposition of macroplastics. The project involved an inspection of the coastline, during which visible macroplastic (objects over 5 mm) was collected and photographed. The photographic documentation also included images of the transect, with particular emphasis on the presence of driftwood, as well as photographs of the tidal zone, illustrating the type of shoreline and the marine vegetation (macroalgae). Additionally, the presence of amphipods and the width of the drift zone were monitored.

Furthermore, during the marine expedition of *s/y Ocean B*, 25 water samples were collected from various locations around the islands of Barentsøya, Edgeøya, and Svenskøya, as well as along the eastern coast of Spitsbergen, for chemical and microbiological analysis. The aim of the study was to monitor the impact of anthropogenic activity, with a particular focus on the presence of pharmaceuticals and antibiotic resistance among bacterial populations.

Figure. 10. Plastic litter mapped on shore of Svenskøya – eastern Svalbard.

Postglacial relative sea-level change on Eastern Svalbard

During the cruise, we visited Svenskøya (Kong Karls Land) in Eastern Svalbard. Svenskøya consists of raised beach ridge plains up to 120 m a.s.l. at both sides of the interior highlands of the island. These beach ridges are the highest observed raised beaches on Svalbard; hence their age is important to constrain the spatial configuration of the last Svalbard-Barents Sea Ice Sheet and the postglacial glacioisostatic rebound and relative sea-level history. We mapped the beach ridges and systematically searched for material (e.g., driftwood, pumice, whale bone) that could provide an absolute age of a beach ridge. This effort resulted in 14 samples of organic material that has been radiocarbon dated. Our oldest dated sample at 61 m a.s.l. has a 2σ age range of 9121-8655 cal. yr BP. With 14 new ages, our new

data will greatly improve the existing relative sea-level knowledge from Svenskøya (Salvigsen, 1981). We are currently analyzing the data and creating digital elevation models of Svenskøya. Four samples of potential pumice were also collected, and these are now in queue for geochemical analyses that can reveal their origin. The expected deliverables is a map of the raised beach ridges with age constraints and a postglacial relative sea level curve valid for Svenskøya and Kong Karls Land. Further, these data aid our understanding of the spatial configuration and ice-load center of the Late Weichselian Svalbard-Barents Sea Ice Sheet.

Figure 11 . Uplifted beach ridges of Svenskøya – one of the key gaps for improving the precision of Holocene relative sea-level changes.

Coastal hazards impact on Cultural heritage - Kapp Pettersen case study

With a warming climate, changing weather patterns and increased erosion from various permafrost- and marine-related processes, the cultural heritage sites in Arctic Svalbard are becoming increasingly vulnerable to destruction. Documentation of cultural heritage in mid to low latitudes is a straightforward process using the latest technological advances, remote sensing techniques and easy access for fieldwork. However, the documentation of such sites in the Arctic Svalbard is very difficult and challenging due to the harsh cold environment, remoteness, limited time to access the sites and obtaining permits from local authorities. During Harsval activity 1.2.1 we aimed: (i) to document a highly isolated and prioritised CH site (the hut at Kapp Pettersen, Svenskøya) using Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and ground photography, (ii) to identify the effects of coastal erosion and permafrost-related processes on the hut, (iii) to have a better understanding of the landscape surrounding the site.

Our initial results highlights the threat of coastal erosion, with an average shoreline retreat of -0.42 m/yr observed between 2010 and 2024. This is significantly higher than those documented at other cultural

heritage sites in Svalbard. Due to the limited number of photos of the hut, it was not possible to make a 3D representation. However, a detailed transcript of the video recording the hut description was made. This highlights the challenges and limitations of Arctic CH documentation. Extended version of the report was submitted as an academic paper for review at *Journal of Cultural Heritage* (Documentation of an isolated and high-priority cultural heritage site in Svalbard. Case study from Kapp Pettersen, Svenskøya by Iwo Wiczorek, Ionut Cristi Nicu, Zuzanna Swirad and Mateusz Strzelecki).

Figure 12. Interior of Kapp Pettersen cabin inspected during the HarSval cruise.

Early Career Research training

The joint Polish-Norwegian cruise provided also a valuable opportunity for the training of yearly career researchers. Alongside experienced professors from Poland and Norway, three junior researchers participated in the cruise. During the expedition, the participants were introduced to the methodology of mapping cultural heritage sites and sampling of uplifted beach material for isotope dating.

Future recommendations

From the coastal environments visited during the research cruise, the following were considered to be the most interesting for the development of further interdisciplinary research:

- a) the rocky shores of Heleysundet, especially the columnar cliffs washed by strong currents and eddies in the strait. Research on the monitoring of cliff erosion, weathering of their surfaces and thermal state of the rockwalls would provide a valuable addition to the research on rocky shores conducted on the west coast.
- b) Dunes and aeolian processes on the south-western coast Svenskøya-Vestletta is probably one of the coastal plains with the highest concentration of various aeolian formations on Svalbard, from sand sheets to barchanoid dunes.
- c) Paraglacial coasts of Kapp Ziehen (Barentsøya), where the Augnebreen moraines transform into an intricate system of ridges and barriers. It is considered to be a prime location for conducting comprehensive research into the mechanisms that govern the transformation of glacial forms left by retreating marine-terminating glaciers into coastal features.

- d) New attempts to collect lake sediment cores from the lake at Seelisberg are also recommended, as it has the potential to record the full history of Holocene environmental changes on the island of Barenstøya.
- e) We are also considering initiatives for the future discussion aimed at researching the interaction between permafrost processes, especially the formation of ice-wedge polygons or hydrolaccoliths, and the role of these processes in disrupting archaeological sites. A good area for this research would be the area between Russe and Kraussbukta, Edgøya.

Conclusions

Polish-Norwegian cooperation is crucial for Svalbard research due to several interrelated factors, including the historical context of scientific collaboration, the strategic importance of Svalbard as a research hub, and the pressing environmental challenges facing the Arctic region.

Historically, Svalbard has served as a significant platform for international scientific collaboration, particularly in the context of the Svalbard Treaty, which allows for the peaceful use of the archipelago for research purposes. The transformation of Ny-Ålesund from a coal mining settlement to a global environmental knowledge center exemplifies this shift towards collaborative research efforts. The Norwegian government has emphasized Ny-Ålesund as a "Norwegian platform for international cooperation in world-class natural sciences research," highlighting the importance of collective scientific agendas in addressing global environmental issues (Paglia, 2019). This cooperative framework is essential for integrating diverse scientific perspectives, including those from Polish researchers who have a longstanding tradition of polar exploration and research (Božek et al., 2024).

Moreover, the unique geopolitical landscape of Svalbard necessitates collaboration among various nations, including Poland and Norway. This dynamic is particularly relevant in the context of climate change, where collaborative research is vital for understanding and mitigating its impacts on Arctic ecosystems and communities.

The strategic importance of Svalbard as a research hub is further reinforced by its role in various international monitoring programs, such as the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) or international observing system for long-term measurements in and around the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard addressing Earth System Science questions (SIOS). These programs rely on contributions from multiple countries, including Poland, to provide comprehensive data on environmental changes and their implications for climate and environmental policy. The collaborative nature of these initiatives not only enhances the scientific output but also strengthens diplomatic ties among participating nations, fostering a spirit of cooperation that is essential for addressing the complex challenges of the Arctic (Rüffin & Rüländ, 2022).

Svalbars coastal research is an area in which coordinated international cooperation is required. Field reconnaissance during the HarSval cruise demonstrated that, in contrast to the relatively well-researched environment of the west coast, the east coast of Spitsbergen and the eastern islands of the Svalbard archipelago have received virtually no research attention with regard to erosion, adaptation to glacial recession and the level of pollution from plastic and other waste.

In conclusion, future Polish-Norwegian cooperation in Svalbard coastal research is crucial due to the historical context of collaborative scientific efforts, the strategic significance of Svalbard as a research hub, and the urgent need to address environmental challenges affecting fragile coastal geoecosystems through multidisciplinary approaches. This cooperation not only enhances the quality and scope of research but also contributes to broader geopolitical stability in the Arctic region.

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